

Adaptation of Cormack Mccarthy's Novels

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Abstract

Adaptation is a process of recreation and reinterpretation. In the post-modern world, adaptation is observed from the point of the viewer's response. When the work is adapted, the reader becomes a viewer. These viewers get connected with the work of art and then the film. Adaptation is the outcome of the filmmaker's readings and interpretations of the source text. Though, the film adaptation of any literary text works, it is an independent, coherent, and artistic creation that carries its own meaning. This adapted artistic work is different from its source text. Most of the adapted works are different from the original source. There are several features of these novels that were difficult to adapt into a film. It was the result of McCarthy's writing style who writes without the use of quotation marks, sometimes it makes challenging to distinguish between characters' dialogue.

Keywords: Adaptation, Cinematography, Screenplay

Introduction

Cormac McCarthy, one of the renowned contemporary American literature writers, has earned a lot of acclaim in recent years of his carrier. The variety of the subject matter that he uses in his writing makes him a conspicuous explorer of a variety of American literary themes like religious, racial, and social issues as well as the significance of familial relationships and the sense of belonging to a place. However, his themes of writing keep on changing with time. Cormac McCarthy, a well established contemporary American writer was born in Providence, Rhode Island on 20th July 1933. He is the eldest of the six kids of his parents, Charles Joseph McCarthy and Gladys Christina McCarthy. His family name was Charles Joseph McCarthy Jr. but he later changed it to Cormac. His family moved to Knoxville, Tennessee in 1937 where, after graduating from high school, he went to the University of Tennessee. However, he left the university in 1953 to join the U. S. Air force where he dedicated four years.

His distinguished novel, *The Orchard Keeper*, was published in 1965. He was sponsored with literary grants so that he could travel to southern Europe, where he

composed his second novel, *Outer Dark* (1968). *Suttree* (1979), like his other early novels, received generally positive reviews but was not a commercial gain. A MacArthur Fellowship helped him to travel to the American Southwest, where he studied and wrote his fifth novel, *Blood Meridian* (1985). Although it initially garnered a lukewarm critical and commercial reception, it is now regarded as his Great American Novel. *All the Pretty Horses* (1992), was his first widespread experience of success, for which he was bestowed upon both the National Book Award and the National Book Critics Circle Award. It was followed by *The Crossing* (1994) and *Cities of the Plain* (1998), completing the Border Trilogy. In 2005, McCarthy came up with *No Country for Old Men*, *The Road*, published in 2006, and the play *The Sunset Limited*, performed in July 2007 at Garage Theatre in Chicago. *The Road* won Pulitzer Prize and the United Kingdom's James Tait Black Memorial Prize for fiction. Most of his works have been adapted into films, for example, *All the Pretty Horses*, *No Country for Old Men*, *Child of God*, *The Sunset Limited*, and *The Road*. The film adaptation of *No Country for Old Men*, directed by Joel and Ethan Coen, won four Academy awards: best picture, best director, best supporting

actor (Javier Bardem), and best adapted screenplay. He has also been awarded with PEN Saul Bellow Lifetime Award in 2009. Today, McCarthy is a writer of ten novels, two plays, and three screenplays and thus has established himself as one of the prominent American writers.

What is Film Adaptation?

A film adaptation is the transfer of a written work, in whole or in part, to a feature film. It is a type of derivative work. A common form of film adaptation is the use of a novel as the basis of a feature film. Other works adapted into films includes non-fiction (including journalism), autobiography, comic books, scriptures, plays, historical sources, and even other films. From the earliest days of cinema, in nineteenth-century Europe, an adaptation from such diverse resources has been an ever-present practice of film-making. The main reason for this particular phenomenon of adaptation of a great book, or, especially, a bestseller may be purely commercial. Reasons. But a skilled and ambitious filmmaker may see in a poorly received or poorly written novel enough visual potential to make a great film.

Adaptation of other fictional forms such as novels, plays, or short stories is mostly used to write a screenplay as they provide an already created plot. Adaptation provides a story for the plot and material to write a screenplay by changing it the way it is suitable for commercial use. The idea of one's own story gives freedom to go for its conversion into the screenplay. In the case of an adaptation, one is required to acquire the rights from the original author or publisher to do so. The original story can be old and may not be very attractive, but a screenwriter has the liberty to use the concept and devise characters with new looks, locations, and situations to suit the movie's requirements. Historical events can also be adapted for dramatization to suit movie making. Acquisition of legal rights is required for a such dramatization of historical events except when all of the principal characters in this dramatization are deceased. In case, a single book is a

source of true historical facts, its adaptation would require the acquisition of legal rights from the author of that book. The strongest and most effective historical movies are those based on contemporary issues, themes, or plot situations placed in a period context, such as examining the contemporary issues of human rights and the morality of war. The contemporary true story can also be a source for the screenplay. An adapted contemporary true story in screenplay means the dramatized account of an actual event as it happens.

Adaptations are understood as a shift from real to fiction that may or may not be true from other points of view. Adaptation is a process of recreation and reinterpretation. In the post-modern world, adaptation is observed from the point of the viewer's response. When the work is adapted, the reader becomes a viewer. These viewers get connected with the work of art and then the film. According to the reader response theory, the reader always remains in the center. Theory gives more importance to the reader, the reader is more important than the text. Adaptation is the outcome of the filmmaker's readings and interpretations of the source text. Though, the film adaptation of any literary text works, it is an independent, coherent, and artistic creation that carries its own meaning. This adapted artistic work is different from its source text. Most of the adapted works are different from the original source. Many films have their roots in literature. George Bluestone, the first scholar of adaptation work said in his book *Novel into Film*, a filmmaker is not a mere translator but an established author.

All The Pretty Horses

All the Pretty Horses portrays the story of a young man from Texas. Though the novel is touching and beautiful, it adds a little bit of the classic edge of a McCarthy story including a heavy focus on nature, the cosmos, and each of our places in the world. The novel opens with the funeral of John Grady Cole's grandfather and his family's decision to sell the family ranch and move. Grady, the protagonist of the novel runs

away and goes towards the Mexican border with his friend Rawlins. In their travel, they are accompanied by Jimmy Blevins and face an array of troubling adventures.

It was Billy Bob Thornton who tried first to bring the writer's work to the screen in the shape of one of his finest novels, *All the Pretty Horses*. The movie was shot in New Mexico and Texas. Thornton's ambitious film, based on the novel of Cormac McCarthy and enacted by Matt Damon, Penelope Cruz, and Henry Thomas, became a challenge when its producer Harvey Weinstein insisted that Thornton must cut the film from three hours down to lesser than two. But Thornton and Damon thought that the removal of Daniel Lanois' score was destroying the movie. On its release in 2000, Weinstein's cut was highly criticized, as Thornton's original version has never seen the light of day.

No Country For Old Men

The second attempt to adapt McCarthy's novel to the screen was far more successful. *No Country for Old Men* is one of McCarthy's distinguished novels. Originally it was written as a screenplay but it was adapted into a novel in 2005. The story of the novel moves around the Mexico/US border during 1980 and follows a drug deal that became wrong. Llewelyn Moss, Anton Chigurh, and Ed Tom Bell are the major characters who deal with the fallout from the drug deal. The novel narrates the story of Llewelyn Moss (Josh Brolin), a hunter who makes a drug deal that goes wrong in the middle of the desert. Moss runs away with a briefcase of cash, unconsciously bringing Chigurh into his life. Sheriff Ed Tom Bell prefers to stay one step behind (Tommy Lee Jones), a contemplative lawman who is going to retire, despairing of the violent world he feels has outpaced him. The Coen brothers adapted the novel in Oscar winning film for, best film, best adapted screenplay, best director, and best supporting actor for Javier Bardem chilling turn. The movie deals with substantial themes of good and evil within a genre framework. It argues that pure evil has always existed among us and it is

unstoppable. It is iniquitous, it has no emotions and it is difficult to be reasoned with this. Indeed, the film's pessimistic ending is unexpected for many viewers, but the movie has the potential as one of the greatest crime films of this century. The film is often considered on critics' "top ten" best films list and is recognized by various writers and critics as one of the best films of its decade. It was even preferred as the 10th best film of the 21st century in 2016.

Child Of God

Child of God is McCarthy's third novel. The novel moves around the protagonist who is a serial killer, operating in the 1960s in Appalachian, Tennessee. It deals with McCarthy's feverish themes of violence and isolation. The novel was adapted into a film, directed by and starring James Franco, in 2013. It also starred Scott Haze, Tim Blake Nelson, and more. The movie was released at the 51st New York Film Festival. Franco as Lester Ballard, in the movie who tries to live outside the boundaries of society. He moves into madness and chaos that deepens as the film goes ahead. There are several features of this novel that were difficult to adapt into a film. It was the result of McCarthy's writing style who writes without the use of quotation marks, sometimes it makes challenging to distinguish between characters' dialogue. He also uses poetic-sounding prose.

The Road

The Road is one more of McCarthy's most successful novels that was translated into a well-loved and award-winning film. The film *The Road* is an adaptation of the Pulitzer Prize winning dystopian novel having the same title. The movie portrays the journey of a father (Viggo Mortenson) and his son (Kodi Smit-McPhee), whose names are implied as only Man and Boy, from an apocalyptic world to a warmer climate.

The novel *The Road* was published in 2006 and adopted into a film in 2008, directed by Joe Hillcoat and based on a screenplay by Joe Penhall. It gained praise from critics around the world and cinematographer Javier Aguirresarobe

received a BAFTA for Best Cinematography.

Conclusion

Adaptation is a process of recreation and reinterpretation. In the post-modern world, adaptation is observed from the point of the viewer's response. When the work is adapted, the reader becomes a viewer. These viewers get connected with the work of art and then the film. Adaptation is the outcome of the filmmaker's readings and interpretations of the source text. Though, the film adaptation of any literary text works, it is an independent, coherent, and artistic creation that carries its own meaning. This adapted artistic work is different from its source text. Most of the adapted works are different from the original source. Cormac McCarthy's novels *All the Pretty Horses*, *Country for Old Men*, *Child of God*, and *The Road* and their adoption in the movies carved great success of the writer, director, and Stars. There are several features of these novels that were difficult to adapt into a film. It was the result of McCarthy's writing style who writes without the use of quotation marks, sometimes it makes challenging to distinguish between characters' dialogue.

References

1. Axelrod, Mark. Once Upon a Time in Hollywood; or, the Commodification of Form in the Adaptation of Fictional Texts to the Hollywood Cinema. *Literature/Film Quarterly* 24.2 (October 1996).
2. Battestin, Martin. Quoted by Wagner, Geoffrey. *The Novel and the Cinema*. Associated University Presses, Inc. 1975.
3. Bandi, Raghu Ram. *Adapting Novels into Films*. Delhi: Prestige Books, 2009. Print.
4. Boyum, Joy Gould. *Double Exposure: Fiction Into Film*. Calcutta: Seagull, 1989. Print.
5. "Film Adaptation." *Wikipedia: The Free Encyclopedia*. Wikimedia Foundation, Inc. On 12 October 2022

6. Hutcheon, Linda. *A Theory of Adaptation*. New York: Routledge, 2006. Print.
7. MacFarlane, Brian. *Novel to Film: An Introduction to the Theory of Adaptation*. Oxford: Clarendon, 1996. Print.